

REGIONAL DEVELOPMENT

PROBLEMS OF TOURISTS ON PILGRIMAGE TOURISM IN TAMIL NADU

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ABSTRACT: The present study has been undertaken from the point of view of tourist. An attempt is made to analyse the problems of pilgrimage tourism in Tamil Nadu and concentrates on the various pilgrimages places and attitude of tourists regarding problems of pilgrimage. This study is limited to the temples of Hindu religion in Tamil Nadu. This study also compares the international tourists and domestic tourists regarding pilgrimage tourism in Tamil Nadu. For the purpose of this study, ten pilgrimage tourist places have been selected, by adopting lottery method. For this study, purposive sampling method was used by the researcher for collecting primary data. The survey was conducted among 800 domestic and 300 foreign tourists. The sample tourists were selected from ten pilgrimage places in Tamil Nadu.

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Introduction

A pilgrimage is a journey or search of moral or spiritual significance. Typically, it is a journey to a shrine or other location of importance to a person's beliefs and faith, although sometimes it can be a metaphorical journey into someone's own beliefs. Pilgrimage tourism, also commonly referred to as faith tourism, is a type of tourism, where people travel individually or in groups for pilgrimage, missionary, or leisure (fellowship) purposes. The world's largest form of mass religious tourism takes place at the annual Hajj pilgrimage in Mecca, Saudi Arabia.

India is a vast land and inhabited by people of various religious faiths. Being a religious land, India is home to innumerable temples, mosques, churches, gurdwaras and other religious structures that are included in pilgrimage tours to India. Tourism is an upcoming and fast growing industry in developing countries like India. Due to its newness in nature, the tourists face some hurdles. This will affect the national economy and the growth of this industry may get affected. This paper focuses on identifying such problems and their intensity level. This paper also analyse the comparison of domestic and foreign tourist for facing problem on pilgrimage tourism in Tamil Nadu.

Tamil Nadu has some of the most remarkable temple architecture in the country, and a living tradition of music, dance, folk arts and fine arts. Tamil Nadu is well renowned for its temple towns and heritage sites. The state boasts the largest tourism industry in India with an annual growth rate of 16%. In 2014, the number of domestic arrivals was at 327.6 million making the state the most popular tourist destination in the country, and foreign arrivals amounted to 4.65 million, the highest in the country, making it the most popular state for tourism in the country.

Scope of the study

The present study has been undertaken from the point of view of tourist. An attempt is made to analyse the problems of pilgrimage tourism in Tamil Nadu and concentrates on the various pilgrimages places and attitude of tourists regarding problems of pilgrimage. This study is limited to the temples of Hindu religion in Tamil Nadu. This study also compares the international tourists and domestic tourists regarding pilgrimage tourism in Tamil Nadu.

Objectives of the study

The objectives of the study are as follows:

1. To find out the problems of tourists regarding pilgrimage tourism in Tamil Nadu.
2. To compare the international tourists and domestic tourists regarding problems on pilgrimage tourism in Tamil Nadu
3. To offer suitable suggestions based on the findings of the study.

Sampling design

Tamil Nadu regions were selected for the study for three reasons. The first is that the Tamil Nadu is the land of temples in India. Secondly, tourism is an emerging sector in Tamil Nadu. Finally, the pilgrimage tourism is a wonderful future in Tamil Nadu region. For the purpose of this study, ten pilgrimage tourist places have been selected, by adopting lottery method.

For this study, purposive sampling method was used by the researcher for collecting primary data. The survey was conducted among 800 domestic and 300 foreign tourists. The sample tourists were selected from ten pilgrimage places in Tamil Nadu.

Problems of tourists on pilgrimage tourism

The sample tourists were asked to respond on three ways 'Yes', 'No' and 'No Opinion' on the following twenty statements framed for the purpose of this study which applies 't' test.

- | | |
|--|---|
| 1. Problems of transportation facilities | 11. Beggar nuisance |
| 2. Lack of accommodation facilities | 12. Problem of tourist guide |
| 3. Poor quality of food and beverages | 13. Problems of tour agent/agency |
| 4. Lack of infrastructure facilities (drinking water, toilet, parking, etc.) | 14. Lack of communication facilities |
| 5. Poor maintenance of pilgrimage | 15. Problems of money exchange |
| 6. Problems of security | 16. Undesirable behaviour of local people |
| 7. Problems of shopping and recreation | 17. Problems of tourism information center |
| 8. Absence/poor condition of medical facilities | 18. Heavy rules and regulations |
| 9. Absence of banking facilities (ATM etc.,) | 19. Illegal collection and corruption |
| 10. Language problem | 20. Higher prices of services in pilgrimage |

Data analysis

Problems of transportation facilities

Table 1 elucidates the details regarding the problems of transportation facilities.

TABLE 1. PROBLEMS OF TRANSPORTATION FACILITIES

SL.No	OPINION	DOMESTIC		FOREIGN	
		NO. OF TOURISTS	PERCENTAGE	NO. OF TOURISTS	PERCENTAGE
1.	Yes	300	37.5	158	52.67
2.	No	500	62.5	142	47.33
3.	No opinion	-	-	-	-
	Total	800	100	300	100

Source: Primary data.

It is inferred from Table 1, out of 800 domestic tourists 37.5% of the tourists have faced the problems of transportation and remaining 62.5% of the tourists do not face any problems on transportation.

Whereas in the case of foreign tourists, out of 300 tourists 52.67% of the tourists have faced the problems of transportation and remaining 47.33% of the tourists do not face any problems on transportation.

Lack of accommodation facilities

Table 2 elucidates the details regarding the problems of accommodation facilities.

TABLE 2. LACK OF ACCOMMODATION FACILITIES

SL.No	OPINION	DOMESTIC		FOREIGN	
		NO. OF TOURISTS	PERCENTAGE	NO. OF TOURISTS	PERCENTAGE
1.	Yes	354	44.25	210	70
2.	No	446	55.75	90	30
3.	No opinion	-	-	-	-
	Total	800	100	300	100

Source: Primary data.

It is inferred from Table 2, out of 800 domestic tourists 44.25% of the tourists have given their opinion that there is an accommodation problem and remaining 55.75% of the tourists have given their opinion that there is no problem on accommodation.

Whereas in the case of foreign tourists, out of 300 tourists 70% of the tourists have given their opinion that there is an accommodation problems and remaining 30% of the tourists do not face any problems on accommodation.

Poor quality of food and beverages

Table 3 elucidates the details regarding the poor quality of food and beverages.

TABLE 3. POOR QUALITY OF FOOD AND BEVERAGES

SL.No	OPINION	DOMESTIC		FOREIGN	
		NO. OF TOURISTS	PERCENTAGE	NO. OF TOURISTS	PERCENTAGE
1.	Yes	446	55.75	203	67.67
2.	No	354	44.25	97	32.33
3.	No opinion	-	-	-	-
	Total	800	100	300	100

Source: Primary data.

It is inferred from Table 3, out of 800 domestic tourists' 55.75% of the tourists have given their opinion that there is a problem of poor quality of food and beverages and remaining 44.25% of the tourists have given their opinion that there is no problem on poor quality of food and beverages. Whereas in the case of foreign tourists, out of 300 tourists 67.67% of the tourists have given their opinion that there is poor quality of food and beverages and remaining 32.33% of the tourists do not face any problems on food and beverages.

Lack of infrastructure facilities

Table 4 elucidates the details regarding the problems of infrastructure facilities.

TABLE 4. LACK OF INFRASTRUCTURE FACILITIES

SL.No	OPINION	DOMESTIC		FOREIGN	
		NO. OF TOURISTS	PERCENTAGE	NO. OF TOURISTS	PERCENTAGE
1.	Yes	574	71.75	233	77.67
2.	No	226	28.25	67	22.33
3.	No opinion	-	-	-	-
	Total	800	100	300	100

Source: Primary data.

It is inferred from Table 4, out of 800 domestic tourists 71.75% of the tourists have given their opinion that there is lack of infrastructure facilities and remaining 28.25% of the tourists have given their opinion that there is no problem on infrastructure facilities in the pilgrimage places. Whereas in the case of foreign tourists, out of 300 tourists 77.67% of the tourists have given their opinion that there is lack of infrastructure facilities problems in the pilgrimage places and remaining 22.33% of the tourists have refused this statement.

Poor maintenance of pilgrimage

Table 5 elucidates the details regarding the poor maintenance of pilgrimage places.

TABLE 5. POOR MAINTENANCE OF PILGRIMAGE

SL.No	OPINION	DOMESTIC		FOREIGN	
		NO. OF TOURISTS	PERCENTAGE	NO. OF TOURISTS	PERCENTAGE
1.	Yes	300	37.5	53	17.67
2.	No	500	62.5	247	82.33
3.	No opinion	-	-	-	-
	Total	800	100	300	100

Source: Primary data.

It is inferred from Table 5, out of 800 domestic tourists 37.5% of the tourists have given their opinion that there is poor maintenance of pilgrimage places and remaining 62.5% of the tourists have given their opinion that there is no problem regarding maintenance of pilgrimage places. Whereas in the case of foreign tourists, out of 300 tourists 17.67% of the tourists have given their opinion that there is poor maintenance of pilgrimage place and remaining 82.33% of the tourists have given their opinion that there is no problem regarding maintenance of pilgrimage places.

Problems of security

Table 6 elucidates the details regarding the problems of security.

TABLE 6. PROBLEMS OF SECURITY

Sl.No	OPINION	DOMESTIC		FOREIGN	
		NO. OF TOURISTS	PERCENTAGE	NO. OF TOURISTS	PERCENTAGE
1.	Yes	290	36.25	60	20
2.	No	510	63.75	240	80
3.	No opinion	-	-	-	-
	Total	800	100	300	100

Source: Primary data.

It is inferred from Table 6, out of 800 domestic tourists 36.25% of the tourists have given their opinion that there is a problem of security and remaining 63.75% of the tourists have given their opinion that there is no problem of security. Whereas in the case of foreign tourists, out of 300 tourists, 20% of the tourists have given their opinion that there is problem of security and remaining 80% of the tourists have given their opinion that there is no problem of security.

Problems of shopping and recreation

Table 7 elucidates the details regarding the problems of shopping and recreation.

TABLE 7. PROBLEMS OF SHOPPING AND RECREATION

Sl.No	OPINION	DOMESTIC		FOREIGN	
		NO. OF TOURISTS	PERCENTAGE	NO. OF TOURISTS	PERCENTAGE
1.	Yes	226	28.25	53	17.67
2.	No	574	71.75	247	82.33
3.	No opinion	-	-	-	-
	Total	800	100	300	100

Source: Primary data.

It is inferred from Table 7, out of 800 domestic tourists 28.25% of the tourists have given their opinion that there is a problems of shopping and recreation and remaining 71.75% of the tourists have given their opinion that there is no problems of shopping and recreation. Whereas in the case of foreign tourists, out of 300 tourists 17.67% of the tourists have given their opinion that there is problems of shopping and recreation and remaining 82.33% of the tourists do not have any problems on shopping and recreation.

Absence/poor condition of medical facilities

Table 8 elucidates the details regarding the absence/poor condition of medical facilities.

TABLE 8. ABSENCE/POOR CONDITION OF MEDICAL FACILITIES

SL.No	OPINION	DOMESTIC		FOREIGN	
		NO. OF TOURISTS	PERCENTAGE	NO. OF TOURISTS	PERCENTAGE
1.	Yes	506	63.25	90	30
2.	No	294	36.75	173	57.67
3.	No opinion	-	-	37	12.33
	Total	800	100	300	100

Source: Primary data.

It is inferred from Table 8, out of 800 domestic tourists 63.25% of the tourists say that there is an absence/poor condition of medical facilities and remaining 36.75% of the tourists have given their opinion that there is no problem of medical facilities in the pilgrimage places. Whereas in the case of foreign tourists, out of 300 tourists 30% of the tourists have given their opinion that there is absence/poor condition of medical facilities and remaining 57.67% of the tourists say that there is no problem of medical facilities. 12.33% of the tourists do not have any opinion on this problem.

Absence of banking facilities (ATM etc.)

Table 9 elucidates the details regarding the absence of banking facilities in the pilgrimage places.

TABLE 9. ABSENCE OF BANKING FACILITIES

SL.No	OPINION	DOMESTIC		FOREIGN	
		NO. OF TOURISTS	PERCENTAGE	NO. OF TOURISTS	PERCENTAGE
1.	Yes	520	65	113	37.67
2.	No	280	35	150	50
3.	No opinion	-	-	37	12.33
	Total	800	100	300	100

Source: Primary data.

It is inferred from Table 9, out of 800 domestic tourists 65% of the tourists have given their opinion that there is an absence of banking facilities and remaining 35% of the tourists have given their opinion that there is no problem of banking facilities. Whereas in the case of foreign tourists, out of 300 tourists 37.67% of the tourists have given their opinion that there is problems of banking facilities and 50% of the tourists do not have any problems on banking facilities. 12.33% of the tourists do not have any opinion on this problem.

Language problem

Table 10 elucidates the details regarding the language problem.

TABLE 10. LANGUAGE PROBLEM

Sl.No	OPINION	DOMESTIC		FOREIGN	
		NO. OF TOURISTS	PERCENTAGE	NO. OF TOURISTS	PERCENTAGE
1.	Yes	186	23.25	240	80
2.	No	614	76.75	53	17.67
3.	No opinion	-	-	7	2.33
	Total	800	100	300	100

Source: Primary data.

It is inferred from Table 10, out of 800 domestic tourists, 23.25% of the tourists have faced the language problems in the pilgrimage places and remaining 76.75% of the tourists do not face any language problems in the pilgrimage places. Whereas in the case of foreign tourists, out of 300 tourists 80% of the tourists have given their opinion that there are language problems and remaining 17.67% of the tourists say than there is no language problem in the pilgrimage places. 2.33% of the tourists do not have any opinion on this problem.

Beggar nuisance

Table 11 elucidates the details regarding the beggar problems in the pilgrimage places.

TABLE 11. BEGGAR PROBLEM

Sl.No	OPINION	DOMESTIC		FOREIGN	
		NO. OF TOURISTS	PERCENTAGE	NO. OF TOURISTS	PERCENTAGE
1.	Yes	386	48.25	188	62.67
2.	No	414	51.75	105	35
3.	No opinion	-	-	7	2.33
	Total	800	100	300	100

Source: Primary data.

It is inferred from Table 11, out of 800 domestic tourists, 48.25% of the tourists have said that there are beggar problems in the pilgrimage places and remaining 51.75% of the tourists have not faced any beggar problems in the pilgrimage places.

Whereas in the case of foreign tourists, out of 300 tourists 62.67% of the tourists have given their opinion that there are beggar problems in the pilgrimage places and remaining 35% of the tourists say than there is no beggar problem. 2.33% of the tourists do not have any opinion on this problem.

Problems of tourist guide

Table 12 elucidates the details regarding the problems of tourists guide.

TABLE 12. PROBLEMS OF TOURISTS GUIDE

SL.No	OPINION	DOMESTIC		FOREIGN	
		NO. OF TOURISTS	PERCENTAGE	NO. OF TOURISTS	PERCENTAGE
1.	Yes	154	19.25	30	10
2.	No	646	80.75	262	87.33
3.	No opinion	-	-	8	2.67
Total		800	100	300	100

Source: Primary data.

From Table 12 we conclude that out of 800 domestic tourists, 19.25% are facing problems with the tourist guide and 80.75% are not having any problems with tourists guide. Likewise, out of 300 foreign tourists, 10% are facing problems with tourists guide, 87.33% are not having any problems with tourists guide and remaining 2.67% do not have any opinion on this problem.

Problems of tour agent/agency

Table 13 elucidates the details regarding the problems of tour agent/agency.

TABLE 13. PROBLEMS OF TOUR AGENT/AGENCY

SL.No	OPINION	DOMESTIC		FOREIGN	
		NO. OF TOURISTS	PERCENTAGE	NO. OF TOURISTS	PERCENTAGE
1.	Yes	140	17.5	30	10
2.	No	660	82.5	240	80
3.	No opinion	-	-	30	10
Total		800	100	300	100

Source: Primary data.

It is inferred from Table 13, out of 800 domestic tourists 17.5% of tourists are not contented with the performance of the tour agent/agency and 82.5% are contented with the performance of tour agent/agency. Likewise, out of 300 foreign tourists only 10% of tourists are not contented with the tour agent/agency, 80% of tourists are contented with the tour agent/agency and remaining 10% do not have any opinion on this problem.

Lack of communication facilities

Table 14 elucidates the details regarding the lack of communication facilities.

TABLE 14. LACK OF COMMUNICATION FACILITIES

SL.No	OPINION	DOMESTIC		FOREIGN	
		NO. OF TOURISTS	PERCENTAGE	NO. OF TOURISTS	PERCENTAGE
1.	Yes	208	26	218	72.67
2.	No	592	74	52	17.33
3.	No opinion	-	-	30	10
Total		800	100	300	100

Source: Primary data.

According to table 14 out of 800 domestic tourists 26% of tourists have problem in communication facilities in the pilgrimage places and 74% of tourists have no problem in communication facilities. Likewise out of 300 foreign tourists, 72.67% of tourists have problems in communication facilities in the pilgrimage places, 17.33% have no problems in communication facilities in the pilgrimage places and remaining 10% do not have any opinion about the problems.

Problems of money exchange

Table 15 elucidates the details regarding the problems of money exchange.

TABLE 15. PROBLEMS OF MONEY EXCHANGE

Sl.No	OPINION	DOMESTIC		FOREIGN	
		NO. OF TOURISTS	PERCENTAGE	NO. OF TOURISTS	PERCENTAGE
1.	Yes	-	-	143	47.67
2.	No	320	40	150	50
3.	No opinion	480	60	7	2.33
	Total	800	100	300	100

Source: Primary data.

From Table 15 we conclude that, out of 800 domestic tourists 40% of tourists are not having any problems on money exchange and remaining 60% of tourists have no opinion on this problem. Likewise, out of 300 foreign tourists, 47.67% of tourists are facing problem with money exchange, 50% are not having money exchange problem and remaining 2.33% have no opinion on this problem.

Undesirable behaviour of local people

Table 16 elucidates the details regarding the undesirable behavior of local people.

TABLE 16. UNDESIRABLE BEHAVIOR OF LOCAL PEOPLE

Sl.No	OPINION	DOMESTIC		FOREIGN	
		NO. OF TOURISTS	PERCENTAGE	NO. OF TOURISTS	PERCENTAGE
1.	Yes	166	20.75	133	44.33
2.	No	634	79.25	160	53.34
3.	No opinion	-	-	7	2.33
	Total	800	100	300	100

Source: Primary data.

It is inferred from table 16, out of 800 domestic tourists 20.67% of tourists are dissatisfied with the behavior of local people and remaining 79.25% of tourists have no problem with behavior of local people. Likewise, out of 300 foreign tourists 44.33% of tourists are dissatisfied with the behavior of local people, 53.34% of tourists have no problems with the behavior of local people and 2.33% of the tourists do not have any opinion on this problem.

Problems of tourism information center

Table 17 elucidates the details regarding the problems of tourism information centre.

TABLE 17. PROBLEMS OF TOURISM INFORMATION CENTRE

Sl.No	OPINION	DOMESTIC		FOREIGN	
		NO. OF TOURISTS	PERCENTAGE	NO. OF TOURISTS	PERCENTAGE
1.	Yes	234	29.25	23	7.67
2.	No	566	70.75	262	87.33
3.	No opinion	-	-	15	5
	Total	800	100	300	100

Source: Primary data.

According to table 17, out of 800 domestic tourists' 29.25% find problem with Tourism Information Centre and remaining 70.75% tourist have no problem with the Tourism Information Centre. Likewise, out of 300 foreign tourists' 7.67% of tourist faced the problems of tourist information centre, 87.33% of tourist have no problems with the tourist information centre and 5% of the tourist do not have any opinion on this problem.

Heavy rules and regulations

Table 18 elucidates the details regarding the heavy rules and regulations in the pilgrimage places.

TABLE 18. HEAVY RULES AND REGULATIONS

Sl.No	OPINION	DOMESTIC		FOREIGN	
		NO. OF TOURISTS	PERCENTAGE	NO. OF TOURISTS	PERCENTAGE
1.	Yes	254	31.75	98	32.67
2.	No	546	68.25	202	67.33
3.	No opinion	-	-	-	-
	Total	800	100	300	100

Source: Primary data.

From table 18 we conclude that out of 800 domestic tourists 31.75% of tourists have faced the problems of heavy rules and regulations and 68.25% of tourists that there are no heavy rules and regulations. Likewise, out of 300 foreign tourists 32.67% of tourists have faced the problems of heavy rules and regulations and remaining 67.33% of tourists that there are no heavy rules and regulation.

Illegal collection and corruption problems

Table 19 elucidates the details regarding the illegal collection and corruption problems in the pilgrimage places.

TABLE 19. ILLEGAL COLLECTION AND CORRUPTION PROBLEMS

Sl.No	OPINION	DOMESTIC		FOREIGN	
		NO. OF TOURISTS	PERCENTAGE	NO. OF TOURISTS	PERCENTAGE
1.	Yes	314	39.25	83	27.67
2.	No	486	60.75	195	65
3.	No opinion	-	-	22	7.33
	Total	800	100	300	100

Source: Primary data.

It is clear from the table 19, out of 800 domestic tourists 39.25% tourists realize that there are illegal collection and corruption problems prevail in pilgrimage places and remaining 60.75% tourists feel that there is no illegal collection and corruption in pilgrimage places. Likewise, out of 300 foreign tourists, 27.67% tourists realize that there are illegal collection and corruption in pilgrimage places, 65% tourists feel that there is no illegal collection and corruption in pilgrimage places and remaining 7.33% tourists do not have any opinion on the illegal collection and corruption problem.

High price of services in pilgrimage

Table 20 elucidates the details regarding the high price of services in pilgrimage.

TABLE 20. HIGH PRICE OF SERVICES IN PILGRIMAGE

Sl.No	OPINION	DOMESTIC		FOREIGN	
		NO. OF TOURISTS	PERCENTAGE	NO. OF TOURISTS	PERCENTAGE
1.	Yes	380	47.5	173	57.67
2.	No	420	52.5	112	37.33
3.	No opinion	-	-	15	5
Total		800	100	300	100

Source: Primary data.

It is inferred from table 20, out of 800 domestic tourists 47.5% of tourists felt that the price of service in pilgrimage are high and 52.5% of tourists felt that the price of services in pilgrimage are moderate.

Likewise out of 300 foreign tourists 57.67% felt that price of services in pilgrimage are high and 37.33% felt that price of services are moderate and remaining 5% of the tourists do not have any opinion on the prices of service.

Two sample t-tests between percents

This test used to compare percentages drawn from two independent samples. Nearly everyone understands percents, and therefore, the researchers are often interested in comparing two percentages to determine whether there is a significant difference between them.

After conducting a survey of tourists, the researcher wants to compare the problems facing of domestic and foreign tourists. Even though all respondents were part of the same survey, the domestic and foreign tourists treated as two samples. The percent of domestic tourists with a particular attribute calculated using the total number of domestic tourists as the denominator for the fraction. And the percent of foreign tourists with the attribute is calculated using the total number of foreign tourist as the denominator. Since the denominators for the two fractions represent different people, a two-sample t-test between percents is appropriate.

The research question is: Is there a significant difference between the problems facing of domestic tourists having the attribute and problems facing of foreign tourists having the attribute?

H₀: There is no significant difference between the problems faced of domestic and foreign tourist in pilgrimage tour. The results of the survey were in table 21.

'T' test has used to test whether there is any significant relationship between problems faced by the domestic and the foreign tourists on pilgrimage tourism. The 'T' Test confirms that there is a significant relationship between the problems faced

by the domestic tourists and foreign tourist except Lack of Infrastructure Facilities (Drinking Water, Toilet, Parking, etc.) and Heavy Rules and Regulations.

TABLE 21. COMPARISON OF DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN TOURIST REGARDING PROBLEMS ON PILGRIMAGE TOURISM - 'T' TEST

Problems	Domestic Tourists		Foreign Tourists		't' - Value	D.F	Two tailed Probability @ 1% level	Hypothesis Accepted/ Rejected	Result
	No. of Tourists Facing Problems	Percentage to Total (800)	No. of Tourists Facing Problems	Percentage to Total (300)					
I.	300	37.5	158	52.67	4.546	1098	.0000	Rejected	Significant
II.	354	44.25	210	70	7.610	1098	.0000	Rejected	Significant
III.	446	55.75	203	67.67	3.580	1098	.0004	Rejected	Significant
IV.	574	71.75	233	77.67	1.978	1098	.0482	Accepted	Not Significant
V.	300	37.5	53	17.67	6.274	1098	.0000	Rejected	Significant
VI.	290	36.25	60	20	5.153	1098	.0000	Rejected	Significant
VII.	226	28.25	53	17.67	3.592	1098	.0003	Rejected	Significant
VIII.	506	63.25	90	30	9.857	1098	.0000	Rejected	Significant
IX.	520	65	113	37.67	8.167	1098	.0000	Rejected	Significant
X.	186	23.25	240	80	17.208	1098	.0000	Rejected	Significant
XI.	386	48.25	188	62.67	4.265	1098	.0000	Rejected	Significant
XII.	154	19.25	30	10	3.661	1098	.0003	Rejected	Significant
XIII.	140	17.5	30	10	3.065	1098	.0022	Rejected	Significant
XIV.	208	26	218	72.67	14.152	1098	.0000	Rejected	Significant
XV.	-	-	143	47.67	20.937	1098	.0000	Rejected	Significant
XVI.	166	20.75	133	44.33	7.829	1098	.0000	Rejected	Significant
XVII.	234	29.25	23	7.67	7.533	1098	.0000	Rejected	Significant
XVIII.	254	31.75	98	32.67	0.291	1098	.7709	Accepted	Not Significant
XIX.	314	39.25	83	27.67	3.562	1098	.0004	Rejected	Significant
XX.	380	47.5	173	57.67	3.004	1098	.0027	Rejected	Significant

Suggestions

The growth of pilgrimage tourism in India has been astonishingly impressive. India is blessed with plenty of well-known religious destinations. Pilgrimages to these destinations bring enormous economic gains to local residents. Pilgrimage tourism reveals the high positive effects of pilgrimage season on income, employment and high standard of living of residents and growth in Tamil Nadu.

The infrastructural facilities such as transportations, sanitation and drinking water facilities are not enough in the pilgrimage tourism centres of the study area. Lack of cleanliness and beggars nuisance are the most important problems faced by the tourists in the study area. Therefore, the government authorities especially the local authorities should pay the special attention on their inconveniences and make necessary arrangements to correct them. The quality of the hospitality service in the study area is found to be poor in the pilgrimage tourism centres of the study area. Therefore, it is suggested that the government authorities should take necessary steps to enhance the quality of the infrastructure and hospitality services provided in the study area.